

1 **A PIECE OF THE ECOTOXICOLOGY PUZZLE: HOW CAN CURRENT AND FUTURE**
2 **RESEARCH INFORM PPD REGULATIONS?**

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48 Abstract

49 2-((4-Methylpentan-2-yl)amino)-5-(phenylamino)cyclohexa-2,5-diene-1,4-dione commonly
50 known as 6PPD-Quinone (6PPD-Q), is the ozonized derivative of, N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-
51 phenyl-p-phenylenediamine, 6PPD. 6PPD is a common tire coating that prevents rubber
52 degradation by acting as an antioxidant. Research efforts elucidating 6PPD-Q's toxicity surged
53 after a 2021 study identified 6PPD-Q as an acute mortality inducing toxicant to coho salmon.
54 This commentary functions as a compilation of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's interaction with aquatic and
55 terrestrial organisms. We also encompass studies providing toxicological explanations of
56 dysregulation of intracellular activity and metabolite transformation. We aim to concurrently
57 impart an overview of the most current 6PPD and 6PPD-Q studies at organismal and cellular
58 levels, emphasize research gaps, such as the lack of global regulations, and propose possible
59 routes for future studies, like the expansion into different model organisms, lifecycle effects,
60 fertility and transgenerational effects, and cancer cell studies.

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62 1. Introduction

63 For years, freshwater environments have been experiencing "urban stream syndrome," a
64 phenomenon attributed to the increased environmental pollutants altering water quality.¹ In
65 urbanized areas, road runoff is a contributing factor to the decline in freshwater habitats. Pacific
66 salmon, specifically coho salmon, are integral to the diverse connection between saltwater and
67 freshwater food webs.² However, coho salmon have been experiencing acute mortality rates
68 when migrating to freshwater ecosystems to reproduce. In 2021, N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-
69 phenyl-p-phenylenediamine-quinone, 6PPD-Quinone (6PPD-Q), was identified as the main
70 contributor to the acute mortality rate seen in coho salmon.³
71 While this revelation is recent, its precursor 6PPD, was originally discovered in the 1960s. 6PPD
72 falls within a class of compounds called p-phenylenediamine (PPD) which are used as
73 antiozonant coatings on rubber tires to prevent breakdown and prolong usage.⁴ Since then,
74 there have been no alternative antiozonants that match 6PPD's ability to prevent rubber
75 breakdown.

76 As such, 6PPD has become a prominent environmental pollutant in recent years. When
77 entering the environment, 6PPD can react with ozone creating 6PPD-Q (Figure 1).⁵ Quinones,
78 when introduced *in vivo*, can induce cytotoxicity, immunotoxicity, or activate detoxification
79 enzymes, depending on their reactivity.⁶ Both molecules are ubiquitous and readily enter the
80 environment through road run-off, rubber waste, and dust, accumulating in both rural and urban
81 waterways (Supplemental Figure 1 and Supplemental Table 1). The half-life of 6PPD is
82 approximately 5 hours in water compared to 6PPD-Q which has a half-life of about 33 hours.⁷
83 Although the half-lives of both chemicals are relatively short, the amount of tires on the road at
84 any given time contribute to the continual leaching of PPDs into waterways. Additionally, even
85 small amounts of PPDs, in the ng/L range, can lead to mortality among aquatic wildlife. This
86 indicates high reactivity. Thus, continued usage of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q has raised concern for
87 aquatic life subjected to these chemicals.

88 Coho salmon seem to be more sensitive to PPDs unlike other freshwater species. The
89 coho salmon mortality discovery has opened the door to a new field in ecotoxicology research
90 (Figure 2). More publications starting in 2021 have revealed species, like zebrafish, with
91 assumed higher tolerances to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.⁷⁻¹⁸ Additionally, other species and *in vitro*
92 models like *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*), when exposed to PPDs, have exhibited
93 metabolic changes and dysregulated genes.^{4,10,19-23} Studies investigating PPD exposure in
94 humans, starting in 2024, reported potential health impacts to those living in areas with high
95 rubber recycling.^{19,20,24-26}

96 Though impacts of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are widespread, there are no global regulations
97 against PPD usage. The United States Environmental Protection Agency, USEPA, is supplying

98 funding to expand the understanding of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's impact and has developed an
99 action plan to mitigate the risks.^{27,28} The United States has completed initial aquatic life
100 screenings to discern the acute exposure levels for 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, 8.9 µg/L and 11 ng/L,
101 respectively.^{29,30} Comparatively, the Canadian Environmental Protection Agency, CEPA, has
102 added PPDs to their substance priority list and are working towards possibly implementing a
103 ban.³¹ The European Union's Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of
104 Chemicals, REACH, is also considering employing restrictions of 6PPD use.³² Whichever
105 country or region can amass sufficient research to support and implement their own regulations
106 will likely help direct other global regulations.

107 Other PPD reviews and commentaries have been published covering environmental
108 impacts on individual species. However, this commentary aims to summarize what has been
109 published thus far about the toxic effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q in multiple aquatic organisms,
110 model organisms, and human cell lines since their discovery in coho salmon. To aid in
111 comparison between species and cell lines, conversions of environmental concentrations (µg/L)
112 of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q to molar concentrations are provided for reference (Supplemental Table
113 2). We aim to point out the gaps occurring within the 6PPD and 6PPD-Q research domain and
114 provide suggestions to drive scientific discovery, understanding, and regulations. Our
115 recommendations include transgenerational studies with a sub focus on epigenetics,
116 toxicological impacts on female model organisms, implementation of fungal models, fate of PPD
117 metabolites, toxicity to cancer cells, single cell sequencing, and coexposure of environmental
118 toxicants.

119
120 Figure 1. Transformation of 6PPD to 6PPD-Q in the presence of ozone (O_3) (created using
121 [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com)).
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123
 124 Figure 2. Timeline of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q development, implementation, and toxic nature
 125 (created using [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com)).
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127 **2. Methods**

128 To gather data, we used the National Library of Medicine (NIH) search engine PubMed.
 129 For example, we used keywords, 6PPD, 6PPD-Q, zebrafish, coho salmon, and *Caenorhabditis*
 130 *elegans* to identify how many papers had been published within this field of study. To further
 131 narrow our search, we included combinations of keywords into our searches such as “6PPD,
 132 zebrafish.” We then sorted through each paper to determine which area of study the paper
 133 focused on and if the information fit into the focus of our manuscript. We were unable to employ
 134 any time restrictions to our searches because all relevant research has been published within
 135 the last five years. Any paper published and available through PubMed was considered for our
 136 commentary.

137 **3. Aquatic Organisms**

138 **3.1 Coho salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*)**

139 Many efforts have been made to thoroughly investigate the consequences of
 140 environmental pollutant 6PPD-Q on coho salmon. Coho salmon are of high ecological
 141 importance because of well-documented “coho pre-spawn mortality” of adult coho salmon
 142 returning to spawn. We believe current findings indicate that even within species, the tolerance
 143 level of 6PPD-Q varies depending on life stage (Table 1). This presents the need to continually
 144 implement the assessment of species’ progressional life stages into toxicology studies.
 145 Investigating embryo tolerance compared to adult coho salmon revealed significant embryonic
 146 mortality which occurred at 7.22 µg/L while adults experienced acute mortality at 1.3 to 1.8
 147 µg/L.^{5,33} Though the adults appear to have decreased tolerance to 6PPD-Q, the variation
 148 between the two studies extended beyond the life stage and into experimental design and study
 149 objectives. Furthermore, we believe the discrepancy in reported tolerance values of juvenile
 150 coho salmon could also be due to contrasts in study designs. One study reported juvenile lethal
 151 concentrations (LC50) as an average of 0.79 ± 0.16 µg/L after only 2 to 6 hours of exposure
 152 whereas another study found a constant 24 exposure decreased the median LC50 to 41.0
 153

154 ng/L.^{3,34} Confirming lethal concentrations for embryonic to adult populations will help inform
155 regulations and preserve sensitive species' populations.

156 **3.2 Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*)**

157 Since the discovery of 6PPD-Q toxicity in coho salmon, research has shifted to using
158 zebrafish embryos and larvae when investigating the effects of environmental levels of 6PPD
159 and 6PPD-Q. The catalyst for the shift being a comparison between the similar life stages. Their
160 short gestational times and transparent bodies make morphological studies simple and
161 accessible. Evidence thus far has categorized zebrafish as a more "tolerant" species.¹⁶ As new
162 studies are published, the effects of PPDs seem to extend beyond mortality and into
163 morphological, behavioral, and physiological changes.

164 **3.3. Zebrafish Mortality**

165 Since zebrafish LC50 values vary so greatly depending on methodology, the definitive
166 categorization of zebrafish may be more nuanced than strictly "tolerant." We find, like the coho
167 salmon studies, the experimental design, data acquisition, and analysis in zebrafish studies
168 makes comparing LC50 values difficult. One study reported the estimated LC50 value for 6PPD
169 to be 442.62 µg/L and 132.92 µg/L for 6PPD-Q after 96 hours of maintained exposure.⁸
170 Alternatively, after 120 hours of stable exposure the measured LC50 value for 6PPD increased
171 to 0.87 mg/L and no effect was found in zebrafish embryos exposed to 6PPD-Q up to 10 mg/L.¹⁸
172 This evidence further highlights the difficulty of comparing mortality rates between and within
173 species.

174 **3.4 Zebrafish Morphology**

175 Multiple studies have also observed morphological alterations in zebrafish. Variable
176 6PPD concentrations resulted in decreases in eye development and eye size, hatchability, body
177 length, and swim bladder size.^{8,10,13,14,18} Comparatively, zebrafish exposed to a range of 6PPD-
178 Q concentrations, had no significant changes to bladder development. However, zebrafish had
179 increased instances of reduced eye size, lordosis, kyphosis, and malformations of the tail.^{8,14,18}
180 While decrease in eye size is consistent between both chemicals, other morphological effects
181 indicate a difference in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's biological targets.

182 **3.5 Zebrafish Behavior and Physiology**

183 Along with morphological changes, PPDs also altered zebrafish behavior and
184 physiological conditions. A cardiovascular trend was seen when investigating the physiological
185 effects of 6PPD-Q at 10-25 µg/L and 20-2000 ng/L respectively. Both discovered 6PPD-Q was
186 linked to cardiotoxicity by way of altered heart rate (BPM).^{8,16} A trend in swim behavior was also
187 seen in both studies as one reported decreases in swim velocity and the other saw reduced
188 locomotive activity.^{8,16} Two studies treated zebrafish larvae with both PPDs for 120 hours and
189 reported behavioral changes. 0.4 mg/L 6PPD was found to inhibit phototactic behavior while 50
190 µg/L of 6PPD-Q was associated with decreased swim distance.^{10,18} After evaluating the
191 presented evidence, we believe it is possible that PPDs interfere with normal swimming
192 behavior typically seen in healthy zebrafish larvae.

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194 **4. Terrestrial Organisms**

195 **4.1 Mice (*Mus musculus*)**

196 Toxic effects of 6PPD-Q have also started to be studied in mammalian models such as
197 male mice. Male mice offer a good fertility model because of their short reproductive times.
198 Across many studies, 6PPD-Q has been found to complicate reproductive processes and

199 induce inflammation responses.³⁵⁻⁴¹ However, there is still a major research gap including
200 female mice models. Because of the wide effects of 6PPD-Q seen in other model organisms as
201 well as male mice, additional studies focusing on female mice models would improve our
202 understanding of the toxic mechanisms of PPDs.

203 The male mice studies have mainly found negative effects in fertility, the inflammatory
204 response, and liver disease. In one study, when injected with 4 mg/kg 6PPD-Q, mouse
205 testosterone levels decreased and sperm quality declined. This led to complications in *in vitro*
206 fertilization (IVF) and suggested impaired male fertility.⁴⁰ Additionally, pathways involving
207 spermatogenesis and sphingolipid metabolism were differentially affected.⁴⁰

208 Furthermore, multiple studies observed fluctuations in inflammation responses. Two
209 studies employed different methods of 6PPD-Q exposure on two mouse models. The first
210 injected 10 and 100 µg/kg for 21 days and the second injected one dose of 4 mg/kg and
211 monitored response over one week. Both saw an increase in the inflammatory cytokines, TNF-
212 α, IL-1, IL-6, and IL-10.^{36,37} A third study injected mice with 0.4 and 4 mg/kg 6PPD-Q every 4
213 days for a 28-day period and saw similar increases in inflammatory cytokines. They also
214 discovered increased instances of apoptosis, blood-brain barrier disruption, and increased
215 levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS).³⁸ 6PPD-Q has also been found to contribute to
216 hepatotoxicity in mice. Long term exposure for 21 days via the oral route, (0.1 and 1 µg/kg bw
217 per day) led to elevated lipid deposition in the liver which can contribute to metabolic
218 dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD).³⁹ These selected male mice studies
219 highlight the various toxic effects of 6PPD-Q.

220 **4.2 Humans (*Homo sapiens*)**

221 Currently, there are no regulations for acceptable daily intake (ADI) or tolerable daily
222 intake (TDI) for PPDs. More studies encompassing dust exposure, human excretions, co-
223 exposure with other toxicants, and transgenerational transmission will give greater insight on
224 exposure level so tolerance can be established. To better understand the effects of 6PPD and
225 its quinone derivative on human health populations, epidemiology studies were carried out in
226 areas with high electronic and rubber waste disposal. In industrialized China, children from ages
227 2 to 7 underwent urine analysis to detect PPDs and results were compared to a control group
228 located farther from the waste disposal site. The median levels of PPDs, 6PPD 0.073 and
229 6PPD-Q 2.34 ng/mL, were reportedly higher for the group in closer proximity to the waste
230 plant.²⁴ Also, dust samples from houses, kindergartens, and road areas with high levels of
231 rubber recycling were compared to a control. For houses and kindergartens, the concentration
232 of 6PPD-Q was reported as higher, 3.2 and 7.5 ng/g, respectively.²⁶ The same study also
233 investigated the presence of polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), polychlorinated
234 biphenyls (PCBs), and heavy metal(loid)s, (Ni and Cu) in kindergarten dust samples. The
235 combination of multitoxicant exposure is thought to be further associated with a decrease in
236 body mass index (BMI), alteration of the gut microbiota, and more frequent illnesses such as
237 influenza, in areas with high rubber recycling.^{25,26} Ingestion of dust in toddlers, approximately
238 3.48 ng/kg bw/d, was suspected to be linked to indoor venues through paint and flooring
239 materials.¹⁹ Although the main focus thus far has been on PPDs effects in children, one study
240 detected the toxicants in breastmilk and adult urine.²⁰ These findings may indicate a possible
241 passage of PPDs and other toxicants from parent to child. Additionally, the showcased studies

242 highlight the presence of both PPDs in areas with high concentrations of rubber recycling and
243 possible interactions with other environmental toxicants.

244 **4.3 *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*)**

245 While 6PPD-Q is often confirmed to be in freshwater environments, it has also been
246 detected in dirt and air samples. 6PPD-Q has been reported to have many negative effects,
247 which is why moving forward *Caenorhabditis elegans* (*C. elegans*) provide a novel avenue to
248 help further understanding of the toxicants biological targets and allow for better informed
249 regulations. *C. elegans* offer unique insight upon 6PPD-Q exposure as they are terrestrial but
250 can appear in aquatic environments.

251 Unlike zebrafish, *C. elegans* do not appear to exhibit drastic changes to morphology or
252 mortality upon 6PPD-Q exposure. Investigating mortality in nematodes revealed only a 5
253 percent mortality rate when subjected to 100 µg/L 6PPD-Q. Though mortality is uncommon in *C.*
254 *elegans*, three studies found 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in a decreased lifespan.⁴²⁻⁴⁵

255 Consistent with zebrafish, 6PPD-Q exposure was linked to behavioral changes in *C.*
256 *elegans*. Two studies found treatment of lower 6PPD-Q concentrations, ranging from 0.1 to 10
257 µg/L, resulted in decreased abnormal locomotion. This was hypothesized to be associated with
258 the neurodegeneration observed in D-type neurons.^{46,47} Neurodegeneration was also observed
259 in dopaminergic, glutamatergic, serotonergic, and GABAergic neurons resulting in decreased
260 sensory perception and neurotransmission.⁴⁶ Comparatively, exposure to 1 to 10 µg/L 6PPD-Q
261 resulted in a decrease of dopamine synthesis leading to a decline in dopamine related
262 behavior.⁴⁷ These studies highlight that 6PPD-Q seems to be a neurotoxin, targeting a multitude
263 of neurons and inhibiting normal behavior.

264 Physiological alterations were also apparent in nematodes, though the processes
265 affected were different than those in zebrafish. Increased intestinal permeability was found in
266 nematodes exposed to 1 to 10 µg/L 6-PPD-Q.^{42,47,48} Metabolism appears to be broadly affected
267 as an increase in fatty acid synthesis resulted in lipid accumulation. Glycogen and glucose
268 metabolism were also inversely affected as 6PPD-Q exposure resulted in an increase of
269 glycogen metabolism and a decrease of glucose metabolism.^{43,45,49,50} Each of these responses
270 across multiple studies indicate the widespread toxic effects of 6PPD-Q. Moving forward,
271 continuing to study metabolic changes in *C. elegans* will lead to a better understanding of
272 6PPD-Q's biological targets.

273
274 Table 1. Summary of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q effect on aquatic organisms, terrestrial organisms, and
275 humans. High effect level indicates mortality at concentrations <100 µg/L 6PPD or 6PPD-Q with
276 severe deformities, and organ dysfunction. Moderate effect level indicates mortality induced at
277 concentrations ≥100 µg/L 6PPD or 6PPD-Q, and/or physiological and behavioral impairment.
278 Low effect level indicates mild or nonlethal effects, and/or limited biological impacts. Effect
279 levels were determined based on the LC50 values, literature, and biological effects.⁵¹

280 *Differences in LC50 values are likely due to differences in experimental design.

	Chemical Treated	LC50	Effect Level	Biological Effects	Findings	References
Coho Salm	6PPD-Q	Embryonic 7.22 µg/L	High	Mortality, morphological, physiological	Decreased size, increased hematocrit	[^{3,5,33,34}]

on		Juvenile* 0.79 µg/L, 41.0 ng/L, 95 ng/L Adult 100 mg/L				
Zebra fish	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	96 hr LC50 6PPD-Q of 132.92 µg/L, 96 hr LC50 6PPD of 442.62 µg/L and 2.2 mg/L, 120 hr IC50 6PPD of 0.87 mg/L*	Moderate	Mortality, morphological, physiological	Decreased eye size, hatchability, body length and swim bladder, decreased swimming and phototactic response, increased sleeping, altered heart rate, cardiac output, oxygen consumption, and hormone and neurotransmitters	[8,10,13,1 4,16,18]
Brook Trout	6PPD-Q	Fry = 0.2 µg/L Fingerlings = 0.5 mg/L	High	Acute mortality, physiological	Increased interlamellar cell mass (ILCM) size, hematocrit, blood glucose, and total CO ₂ . Decreased blood sodium and chloride concentration	[52]
Rainb ow Trout	6PPD-Q	1.00 µg/L and 2.08 µg/L*	High	Acute mortality, physiological	Increased cardio respiration, respiration, and metabolism	[53,54]
Arctic Char	6PPD-Q	N/A	Low	Physiological	Increased metabolism	[53]
Lake Trout	6PPD-Q	96 hr = 0.50 µg/L	High	Acute mortality, morphological	Caudal fin and eye deformities	[55]
Mice	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	N/A	Moderate	Physiological	Decreased testosterone, sperm quality, altered spermatogenesis, and sphingolipid metabolism pathways.	[36-40]

Humans	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	N/A	Moderate	Physiological	Increased inflammation and lipid accumulation Decreased BMI, altered gut microbiome, and increased susceptibility to illnesses	[19,20,24-26]
C. Elegans	6PPD-Q	100 µg/L	Moderate	Moderate lethality, behavioral, physiological	Altered locomotion, increased intestinal permeability, neurodegeneration, lipid accumulation and glycogen metabolism. Decreased glucose metabolism and dopamine synthesis	[42-50,56-58]

281

282 5. Mechanistic Research for PPDs

283 5.1 PPDs and Metabolic Fate

284 The complete metabolism of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q is still largely unknown. However,
285 several studies have identified cytochrome p450 enzymes, CYP1A, CYP3A, 3A4, and 2C19, as
286 integral to the metabolic breakdown of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.^{21,22,59} When CYP1A was inhibited by
287 α -naphthoflavone (ANF) and quercetin, the levels of unmetabolized 6PPD-Q increased,
288 indicating its enzymatic activity is imperative.²²

289 There still remains a need to identify transformation products (TPs) as potential
290 biomarkers. Of the many papers discussed below, the main focus was that of PPDs and how
291 they interact with metabolic proteins focusing on the short biological half-life of the toxicants.
292 PPDs have been studied in *in vivo* and *in vitro* models including zebrafish, mice, human and rat
293 liver microsomes, rainbow trout liver cells (RTL-W1), and human liver cell lines (L02 and
294 HepG2).^{7,12,21-23,60} For example, the half-life of 6PPD-Q was studied in mice blood, urine, and
295 feces (5.32, 6.20, and 3.87 hours respectively).²³ When studying transformation products of
296 toxicants, typically transformations are labeled as Phase I and Phase II metabolites with
297 subsequent modifications. Across species, the TPs may vary depending on the metabolic
298 pathways used to detoxify 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Two transformations of 6PPD-Q, hydroxylation,
299 being the most commonly reported, and glucuronidation, have been identified across species as
300 metabolites.^{7,12,21,23,60,61} Thorough research has indicated strong potential for hydroxylation and
301 glucuronidation TPs to act as effective biomarkers for 6PPD-Q exposure, further investigation is
302 needed to identify possible biomarkers for 6PPD's metabolism.

303 5.2 PPDs and Protein Interactions

304 The metabolic breakdown and widespread protein interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q
305 complicate our full understanding of their toxicological implications. Solidifying metabolic
306 biomarkers for both PPDs is the first step towards understanding how these toxicants interact *in*
307 *in vivo* and *in vitro*. PPDs have been reported to interact with proteins affiliated with blood,
308 neurons, and cancer. Molecular docking has shown 6PPD and 6PPD-Q forms complexes with

309 human serum albumin (HSA), alters the secondary structure, and differentially affects the
310 esterase activity.⁶² 6PPD-Q has also been shown to interact with neuronal proteins involved in
311 neurotransmitter reception and synthesis, for example BAS-1, GLB-10, and
312 acetylcholinesterase.^{46,47,63} These interactions are likely the basis for the neurotoxicity seen in
313 the presence of 6PPD-Q. Molecular docking has also uncovered 6PPD-Q's potential effect on
314 prostate cancer signaling pathway proteins. Normally, JAK2 is involved in regulating the cell
315 cycle, but since it has strong binding affinity with 6PPD-Q, this has implications regarding the
316 metastasis of prostate cancer.⁶⁴ Seeing that both PPDs have a high likelihood of interacting with
317 a broad range of proteins, uncovering the full scope of these interactions is key to piecing
318 together the toxicology picture.
319

320 **6. PPDs and Gene Regulation Related to the Immune Response**

321 **6.1 Gene Regulation Prior to the Inflammatory Response**

322 Current research indicates a trend in 6PPD and 6PPD-Q's proclivity to prompt an
323 organism's immune response, primarily via the organism's inflammation pathway.
324 We aim to distinguish differences in an organism's gene regulation seen leading up to, during,
325 and after the inflammatory response. This area of research is particularly rich, though recent
326 publications indicate a need to map what is currently known across species in terms of the
327 immune response (Figure 3).

328 Prior to inducing an inflammatory response, PPDs create a stressful environment that
329 results in cellular oxidative damage. This is characterized by an elevation of ROS levels. Many
330 studies directly measured ROS levels following 6PPD treatment and found an increase in ROS
331 in embryonic, larval, and adult zebrafish.^{11,12,65-68} In comparison, 6PPD-Q was found to induce
332 oxidative stress within human liver cell lines, like L02 and HepG2, as well as in *C. elegans* and
333 mice.^{22,37,41,47,69,70}

334 To further confirm the presence of increased ROS following PPD treatment, researchers
335 have analyzed the regulation of antioxidant genes responsible for mediating oxidative stress like
336 SOD-2, SOD-3, and SOD-4. Two studies found increased expression of antioxidant genes,
337 further indicating oxidative stress is caused by PPDs.^{41,63} *C. elegans*, tend to employ the
338 mitochondrial unfolded protein response (mt UPR) in the presence of oxidative stress.
339 Specifically, this response is mediated by *set-6*, *met-2*, *jmjd-1.2*, and *jmjd-3.1*. These genes
340 were dysregulated in the presence of 6PPD-Q, thereby hindering the mt UPR response and
341 increasing *C. elegans*' susceptibility to oxidative damage.^{71,72} Consistent exposure to PPDs may
342 prolong the stressful cellular conditions causing continued ROS production. ROS then act as
343 signaling molecules launching an inflammation response.⁷³

344 **6.2 Gene Regulation During the Inflammatory Response**

345 After consistent PPD exposure elevates ROS, an inflammatory response is generated by
346 the upregulation of proinflammatory genes. These genes code for cytokines which activate the
347 immune response and participate in their own positive feedback mechanism.^{72,74} Classifications
348 for cytokines include tumor necrosis factors, interleukins, and chemokines.⁷⁵

349 In mice, zebrafish, and human lung and endometrial epithelial cells, 6PPD exposure most
350 notably appeared to cause gene dysregulation of cytokines TNF α .^{35,66,76,77} Upregulation of TNF α
351 implies the propagation of inflammation pathways NF- κ B and MAPK. NF- κ B helps to mediate
352 aspects of innate and adaptive immunity while also creating a positive feedback loop by
353 proliferating further waves of cytokines (Table 2).⁷⁸ With cytokines' ability to create a positive
354 feedback loop, chronic inflammation is possible.

355 Gene dysregulation of cytokines following 6PPD-Q exposure has been analyzed more
356 thoroughly in coho salmon, mice, and humans.^{5,36,37,66} Similar to organisms exposed to 6PPD,
357 the quinone derivative also caused an upregulation of cytokine TNF α . Again, confirming
358 activation of the NF- κ B and MAPK pathways. 6PPD-Q also upregulated the expression of

359 cytokines IL-6, Ripk1, and Fadd indicating JAK-STAT, necrosis, and apoptosis may also be
 360 prompted. Additionally, this has been shown to further disrupt genes regulating metabolism of
 361 macromolecules.

362 6.3 Gene Regulation Following the Inflammatory Response

363 6PPD exposure has been well documented to dysregulate lipid metabolism in zebrafish.
 364 Multiple studies find an increased expression of genes regulating fatty acid synthesis, like *ppary*
 365 and *fasn-1*, while there was a decreased expression of genes regulating β -oxidation like *acs-2*
 366 and *ech-2*.^{61,77,79,80} Dysregulation of lipid metabolism was further evidenced by an increase in
 367 triglyceride and cholesterol levels. In studies treating zebrafish and *C. elegans* with 6PPD-Q,
 368 upregulated lipid synthesis and downregulated β -oxidation were also prevalent.^{15,49}

369 Though there is evidence of other biomolecules, like glucose, with disrupted metabolism,
 370 lipids have been by far the most studied.⁵⁹ Consequences may extend beyond gene
 371 dysregulation of lipids following continued PPD exposure. As mentioned before, following three
 372 weeks of 6PPD-Q exposure, mice displayed disrupted lipid metabolism which culminated in fatty
 373 liver disease.³⁹ For aquatic organisms known to experience long term exposure of the tire
 374 pollutants, this raises a serious risk of hepatotoxicity. Long term damage to the liver may further
 375 exacerbate the inflammatory response already prompted by the cellular stress of PPDs.

376
 377 Table 2. Gene and protein dysregulation in coho salmon, zebrafish, mice, *C. elegans*, and
 378 endometrial epithelial cells and their morphological effects.

	Chemical Treated	Genes and Proteins Dysregulated	Alterations to
Coho Salmon	0.1-7.2 μ g/L 6PPD-Q	TNF α , il1 β , JAM, and ifny	Blood brain barrier, vascular permeability, and inflammation
Zebrafish	2.2 mg/L 6PPD and 0.25-25 μ g/L 6PPD-Q	<i>rpe65a</i> , <i>opn1lw1</i> , <i>per1a</i> , <i>per3</i> , and <i>cry3a</i>	Thyroid signaling pathway, eye development, estrogen signaling and circadian rhythm
Mice	10-100 mg/kg 6PPD and 6PPD-Q	Ripk1, Fadd, Il-6st, and Il-16	Immune system, macrophage infiltration, and prostate cancer activation
Endometrial Epithelial Cells	1-10 μ M 6PPD and 1 μ M 6PPD-Q	TNF α , IL6, and TGF β 1	Endometrial receptivity and inflammatory responses
<i>C. elegans</i>	10 μ g/L 6PPD-Q	<i>atfs-1</i> , <i>ubl-5</i> , <i>dve-1</i> , <i>fasn-1</i> , and <i>pod-2</i>	Mitochondrial unfolded protein response and lipid accumulation

379
380 Figure 3. Comprehensive overview of known interactions of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q (created using
381 BioRender.com).

382 383 7. Recommendations in PPD Research

384 Through this literature search we aimed to summarize the toxicological effects of PPDs,
385 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, on aquatic and terrestrial organisms and point out the major gaps that need
386 to be addressed as regulations are developed. After compiling data covering *in vivo* and *in vitro*
387 models, it is clear that 6PPD and 6PPD-Q have some overlapping toxic effects but also some
388 distinct characteristics. Throughout our commentary we discussed progressional life stages for
389 coho salmon and zebrafish. We believe a good foundation has been laid outlining the lifecycle
390 effects. While this area of study is still important, we think it can be deprioritized moving forward
391 in the PPD research field. Instead, integrating interdisciplinary research methods will help
392 increase knowledge and help inform global regulations (Figure 4). We specifically recommend
393 focusing on discerning the toxic mechanisms of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q through the following
394 routes:

395 **7.1 Transgenerational Studies.** A considerable amount of research has been published
396 covering lifecycle effects of PPDs, however there remains a noticeable absence of research
397 establishing the inheritance of epigenetic changes and mutations. Given that some species are
398 evidenced to be more tolerant to 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, we expect to see a similar trend of toxic
399 effects in future generations. To remedy this, employing multiple generational studies focusing
400 on epigenetic changes will give key insights to the long-term repercussions of PPD usage.

401 **7.2 Female Model Organisms.** As of now, the majority of rodent toxicology studies
402 have explored the effects of 6PPD-Q on the male mouse model finding defects in the process of
403 spermatogenesis. While these discoveries are highly relevant, uncovering the effects on female
404 reproduction are of equal importance. To bridge this gap, we recommend implementing female

405 rodent studies in parallel to the already completed male rodent studies. Furthermore, including
406 both male and female models in studies will ensure parallel information is being reported.

407 **7.3 Fungal Cell Toxicology and Metagenomics.** Fungi are an integral aspect of water
408 ecosystems. Fungal communities give vital information about the health of the ecosystem they
409 reside in. No studies have ventured into the effects of PPDs on fungal cells. This could be an
410 interesting approach to discern effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. As fungal cells are single-celled
411 eukaryotes, cell trafficking and protein interactions can easily be studied. Implementation of
412 yeast studies opens the door to faster turnaround of data acquisition as well as multi-faceted
413 research approaches, such as metabolomics, metagenomics, transcriptomics, and
414 bioaccumulation.

415 **7.4 Fate of Metabolites and their Interactions *in vivo*.** A preliminary foundation of
416 6PPD and 6PPD-Q metabolites has been formed. However, many metabolites have been
417 identified, as either Phase I or Phase II, but the research has stalled there. The continued
418 breakdown mechanisms and pathways of transformation products is important in identifying all
419 exposure biomarkers. We suggest implementing high performance liquid chromatography
420 coupled with mass spectrometry into metabolite studies at various life stages. Ultimately,
421 uncovering the pathways used to metabolize 6PPD and 6PPD-Q will aid in our understanding of
422 their mechanistic impact and identify screenable biomarkers.

423 **7.5 PPD Effects on Cancer Cell Lines.** Using cancer cells as a model system is useful
424 because of the ease of culturing and wide availability. Since cancerous cell lines are
425 immortalized, making long term studies investigating toxicological effects of PPDs possible.
426 Currently, there is an insufficient amount of research investigating how PPDs interact with
427 cellular components. To build upon current findings, studies should investigate effects on cell
428 viability, apoptosis, and ROS formation in additional cell lines following PPD treatment. We also
429 suggest pivoting towards studies evaluating ATP production, lipid peroxidation, and cell
430 trafficking. Implementing these assessments is essential to uncovering the mechanisms behind
431 PPD toxicity and serve as a good path to uncovering metabolic fate.

432 **7.6 Single-cell Sequencing (SCS).** Single-cell sequencing has many advantages such
433 as uncovering discrepancies in cell population responses, pinpointing exact toxicity limits, and
434 providing insight into dynamic cellular responses. There has been an effort to perform bulk
435 sequencing especially for transcriptomic studies. However, these types of experiments can
436 sometimes lose the nuanced responses from individual cells within a population. Implementing
437 this technique into PPD toxicology studies may help reveal novel information like sensitivity
438 limits, how different cell types, and organ systems respond to PPD exposure.

439 **7.7 Coexposure of Environmental Toxicants.** 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are not isolated
440 toxicants. The likelihood of multiple toxic chemicals, like PHAs and metalloids, interacting with
441 PPDs is high. Limited information has been published encompassing coexposure in humans.
442 We specifically note that there have not been any coexposure studies conducted using coho
443 salmon. Investigating coexposure of PPDs with other prominent environmental toxicants in as
444 many model organisms as possible would give insightful information on how different toxicants
445 interact synergistically, antagonistically, or not at all. Additionally, any interactions that are
446 discovered will only bolster the scientific evidence needed to implement strict regulations of
447 PPDs.

448
449 All the above-mentioned future research trends are equally important in advancing
450 scientific understanding of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. Collectively, each area of emphasis will bridge
451 the gaps in knowledge and provide a more thorough understanding of tire pollutant impacts.
452 Eventually, this ground-breaking research will help formulate regulations and combat the toxic
453 effects of PPDs.

454
455 **Author Contributions**

456 E.B.: writing-original draft preparation, review, editing; M.M.: writing-original draft preparation,
457 review, editing; K.K.: review, editing, and supervision. All authors have read and agreed to the
458 published version of the manuscript.

459

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463

464 **Disclosure of interest**

465 The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

466

467 **Data Availability Statement**

468 Data sharing is not applicable as no new data was created or analyzed in this review.

469

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475

476 **Abbreviations**

477 6PPD: (N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-phenyl-p-phenylenediamine)

478 6PPD-Q: N-(1,3-dimethylbutyl)-N'-phenyl-p-phenylenediamine-quinone

479 USEPA: United States Environmental Protection agency

480 PPD: p-Phenylenediamine

481 CEPA: Canadian Environmental Protection Agency

482 REACH: Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals

483 NIH: National Institute of Health

484 LC50: Lethal concentration 50

485 UPLC-QE: Ultra performance liquid chromatography - Q Exactive Focus Orbitrap mass
486 spectrometry

487 BPM: beats per minute

488 IVF: *in vitro* fertilization

489 TNF α : Tumor Necrosis Factor - α

490 IL-1: Interleukin-1

491 IL-10: Interleukin-10

492 IL-6: Interleukin-6

493 *Il1b*: interleukin 1 *b* gene
494 *per1a*: period circadian clock 1 a gene
495 *per3*: period circadian regulator 3
496 *cry3a*: cryptochrome circadian regulator 3a
497 Ripk1: receptor-interacting serine/threonine-protein kinase 1
498 Fadd: fas-associated death domain
499 Il-6st: interleukin 6 Cytokine Family Signal Transducer
500 Il-16: interleukin-16
501 *SOD-2*: superoxide dismutase 2 gene
502 *SOD-3*: superoxide dismutase 3 gene
503 *SOD-4*: superoxide dismutase 4 gene
504 ROS: reactive oxygen species
505 MASLD: metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease
506 BMI: body mass index
507 PBDE: polybrominated diphenyl ethers
508 PCB: polychlorinated biphenyls
509 Ni: Nickel
510 Cu: Copper
511 ADI: Acceptable daily intake
512 TDI: Tolerable daily intake
513 ILCM: Interlamellar cell mass
514 L02: Human liver hepatocyte
515 HepG2: Hepatocellular carcinoma
516 TP: Transformation product
517 Mt UPR: Mitochondrial unfold protein response
518 *atfs-1*: Activating transcription factor associated with Stress-1
519 *ubl-5*: Ubiquitin-like protein 5

520 *dve-1*: Homeobox transcriptional regulator
521 *fasn-1*: Fatty acid synthase 1 gene
522 *pod-2*: Acetyl-CoA Carboxylase gene
523 p450: Cytochrome p450 protein
524 CYP1A2: Cytochrome p450 1A2
525 CYP3A: Cytochrome p450 3A
526 2C19: Cytochrome p450 2C19
527 ANF: α -naphthoflavone
528 BAS-1: Cytochrome p450 superfamily protein
529 GRB-10: Globin like protein 10
530 JAK2: Janus kinase 2
531 SOD: Superoxide dismutase
532 HSA: Human serum albumin
533 NF- κ B: Nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated

534

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536

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Supplemental Figure 1. World map detailing locations that have detected 6PPD and 6PPD-Q (created using Biorender.com).

Supplemental Table 1. Countries with 6PPD and/or 6PPD-Q detected in local samples.

Country	Location of Sample Site	Chemical	References
Argentina	Buenos Aires	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Australia	Queensland (Brisbane River)	6PPD-Q	[^{82,83}]
Brazil	São Paulo	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Canada	Southern Ontario (Don River and Highland Creek) and Toronto	6PPD-Q	[^{81,84–86}]
Chile	Santiago	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
China	Guangzhou (Liuxi River and Guanghua Basin), South China (Greater Bay Area), Guangdong (Pearl River and Dongjiang river), Zhejiang (Zhujiang river and Jiaojiang River), Yangtze River, Taiyuan, Zhengzhou, Shanghai, Nanjing, Hangzhou, and Hong Kong	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	[^{19,87–99}]
Colombia	Bogota	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Germany	Leipzig Saxony	6PPD and 6PPD-Q	[^{100–103}]

India	Kolkata and New Delhi	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Japan	Tokyo	6PPD-Q	[^{81,104}]
Nigeria	Lagos	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Poland	Warsaw	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
Spain	Madrid	6PPD-Q	[⁸¹]
USA	California (San Francisco Bay), Colorado, Georgia, Kansas, Michigan, Minnesota, Mississippi (Oxford), New York, North Carolina, Oklahoma, Oregon, Texas, Virginia, and Washington (Tacoma)	6PPD-Q	[¹⁰⁵⁻¹⁰⁹]

955 Supplemental Table 2. Common concentrations of 6PPD* and 6PPD-Q* listed as micrograms
956 per liter ($\mu\text{g/L}$) and corresponding conversion to nanomolar (nM).

6PPD ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	6PPD (nM)	6PPD-Q ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	6PPD-Q (nM)
0.1	0.370	0.1	0.340
5	1.86	5	1.68
10	3.73	10	3.35
50	18.6	50	16.8
100	37.3	100	33.5
500	186	500	167.6
1000	373	1000	335

957 *Based on molar masses 6PPD, 268.4 g/mol and 6PPD-Q, 298.4 g/mol
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